

Original Article

STAKEHOLDERS PARTICIPATION IN THE FUNDING PRACTICES OF PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS, ENUGU STATE, NIGERIA.

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Abstract

The study is anchored on stakeholder's participation in the funding practices of public secondary schools in Enugu state. Three research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population for the study was 297 secondary school principals' in Enugu state. A self-structured questionnaire developed by the researchers, titled "stakeholder's participation in funding practices questionnaire" (SPFPQ) was used for data collection. This instrument was validated by three experts, two from the Department of Educational Management and one from Mathematics and Computer Education Department (Measurement and Evaluation option). Reliability coefficient of .74 was established using Cronbach Alpha reliability estimate. Mean with standard deviation was used to answer the research questions. *t* test statistic was used in analyzing the hypotheses at .05 level of significance. The findings of the study among others revealed that stakeholder's participation in funding practices of secondary education in Enugu State is inadequate. The researchers recommended among others that stakeholder's in education should be encouraged for active participation in the funding practices of public secondary schools in Enugu State to enhance the output.

Keywords: Stakeholders, Participation, Funding Practices, Public Secondary Schools.

Introduction

Education has become a very big enterprise all over the globe. It has become a microscope through which ones potentials are detected and channeled appropriately. According to Ihienyemolor (2023), the importance of education to every citizen has also become a central issue for discussion in very many global flora, therefore the need for increase in access and justification for all human and material investment in education. The quality of any nation according to Nwangwu (2016) depends on the quality

and quantity of products that its educational institutions are able to turn out in the labour market. Where the turnout is weak, the country is bound to be weak, technologically, socially, economically, politically and vice versa. The output quality of these products however, depends majorly on the stakeholder's commitment and funding practices deployed for the sustainability of the educational institutions particularly Secondary Education. Secondary education which is the area of focus, according to Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013) in her National Policy on Education stated that it is the education children receive after primary education

and before the tertiary stage. This stage may be seen as the level that prepares a child for useful living within the society and for higher education. The heads of secondary schools are called principals who can be male or female. They are employed in public secondary schools and may be regarded as the chief administrators of their different schools.

Principals', according to Okogbaa (2020) are the chief administrators of Secondary Schools. They hold presiding rank, are leaders, and are accountable for managing the major administrative tasks and supervision of all staff and students to promote the success of all the students in particular and the schools at large. They are one of the stakeholders in secondary schools. The author further stated that in Nigeria Educational System, "principal" is the title given to heads of Secondary Schools both Junior and Senior Secondary. The appointment /selection of public secondary school principals' usually follow due process focusing on length of time as classroom teacher, qualifications, and capacity to hold the office (Orunbon 2023). The appointment may be seen as gender friendly.

Gender therefore, as viewed by Canadian Institute of Health Research (2023) is socially constructed roles, behaviours, expressions, and identities of girls, women, boys, men and gender diverse people. It influences how people perceive themselves and each other, how they act and interact, and the distribution of power and resources in society.

Public Secondary Schools are Government owned schools (Pennsylvania 2025). In other words, they are funded, maintained, and managed by various levels of Government. Government is the major stakeholder in the management of public secondary schools. Stakeholders in education however may be perceived as people who have invested or are interested in the system. Stakeholders in education as defined by Watt and Roundy (2022) are those who have stake or vested interest in the success and welfare of a school or educational system. Similarly, the Glossary of Education Reform (2014) also defined stakeholders in

education as those who have interest or have invested interest in the welfare and success of an institution. These people may have engaged in any educational related activities. This group of people may include those with direct involvement such as: teachers, administrators, parents, school boards and students. While those who are indirectly involved may include: communities, government at all levels, Parents Teachers Association (PTA) or School Based Management Committee (SBMC), old students' unions, tax payers, civil society organizations, alumni, policy makers and philanthropists. These people can be instrumental to the success or failure of the educational system.

Though, the government is the major stakeholder in the funding of public secondary schools in Enugu State, the researchers are interested in the extent of participation of old students', PTA/SBMC and the host community in funding public secondary schools. Old students are those who have graduated from these public secondary schools and are found in different fields of life doing well. According to Gustavsen (2024) old Students/Alumni is an association of graduate students of a particular institution. It is a community that brings former students together.

PTA/SBMC involves parents, teachers, faith organizations, students, civil society organizations, the Igwe of the host community and his cabinet members, women organization and a host of others who have interest in the education of their children. PTA (Parents Teachers Association) according to Lineberger is a school based organization that enables parents to support the operations of their children's school. It is school based organization with the mission of making the school a better place for children to study. In accordance with the government policy on education, SBMC was established in 2007 by Federal Ministry Education (FME) (Agundu, Njoku and Okpala 2024). The aim was to decentralize the authority, ensure community participation in school management and improve accountability and educational outcomes.

In the same manner, host community is the community where the school is located. This host community is the direct beneficiary of the dividend of the secondary school education, therefore are expected to do everything possible to safeguard and ensure adequate support for the progress of the school. Community as it sounds is a unified body of individuals with common interests, living in a particular area (Marrian-Webester 2025). They may be a group of people with common characteristic or interest living together within a larger society.

The involvement of the community in the administration of public secondary schools can improve communication and understanding of the need and the way of working with an institution. It may also bring about the perspective experience and expertise of participating community members who can propose reforms, strategies that will lead to quality enhancement and attainment of the educational goals. Every stakeholder in education has a purpose. A stakeholder working with other stakeholders, sharing ideas and plans may often achieve common educational objectives. This team effort improves the chances of realizing those goals and creating positive students outcomes. They may aim at ensuring that students receive quality education through adequate instruction which prepares them for life after school as productive members of the society. This positive outcome in other words may strengthen the community as a whole.

The participation of these stakeholders in Enugu state public secondary schools is unavoidable as schools seem not to survive holistically without their support. According to Amann (2023) participation, is action that starts from resources, which are dependent on social forms of organization, in its execution and produces its effects in the context of social integration. This action is controlled by potentials or resources that are found both in an individual and in

the environment. In the view of Stanley (2023) participation is the act of people being involved in decision that affects their lives. This decision can be positive or negative. Through participation, such people can identify opportunities and strategies for action and then build solidarity to effect change. One may say that meaningful participation is dependent on people's willingness and ability to participate and express their opinions. Stakeholder's participation in public secondary schools may be challenging where there are lack of certain knowledge and relevant language to understand and contribute, or even feel they do not have the right to participate. All these challenges notwithstanding, public secondary school education in Nigeria and Enugu state in particular must be moved to a greater height and this can only be done through adequate funding practices.

Funding of education according to Manuel (2016) is a set of regulations and procedures used to allocate money and resources for the harmonious and effective functioning of educational institutions. It may be the practice of providing money to organizations, institutions or individuals for a particular purpose. Funding of education in Enugu state seems to be a great problem for decades of years now. This has been a big problem to the education system. This problem however, is yet to be solved fully.

The benchmark initiated by United Nations Education Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), which according to Nwangwu (2016) stipulated 26 percent of the country's yearly budget and vision 2010 committee recommendation of 15 percent of the annual budget for education has never been met. All these have always been in theory and that is what the Education system suffers. To solidify this fact, the budget for Enugu State Post Primary School Management Board (PPSMB) for the past three years has been inadequate to meet up with the demand. See the table below:

Year	Recurrent Expenditure	Capital Expenditure	Total
2021	10,352,823,303.00	673,700,000.00	10,990,523,303.00

2022	11,017,322,188.00	508,560,000.00	11,525,882,188.00
2023	10,361,721,390.00	663,000,000.00	11,024,721,390.00

Source: Enugu State Ministry of Budget and Planning (2023).

Based on the illustration above, one may say that there is fluctuation in funds provided for education and this makes it difficult for adequate planning taking into cognizance the number of students and schools involved. This has led to the proliferation of private secondary schools in the state. In any case, this does not mean that the government is not making any effort but other sources should be opened up for adequate funding practices.

Equally, adequate funding according to Ogadinma and Jack (2023) should be able to provide adequate resources, maintain infrastructure and support the overall learning experience of students. Though the funding is inadequate, the Government plays a significant role in financing public secondary schools. In any case, there is that growing tendency of the importance of stakeholder's participation in the funding practices. Insufficient funding can hinder the quality of education, create severe disparities and impede students' success. Based on that, funding of education should not be left at the mercy of the government alone, be it federal, state, and local governments. Stakeholders in education therefore, should work as a team to complement and supplement each other morally, socially and financially in achieving the desired educational goals.

Statement of the Problem:

The policy declaration of Federal Government of Nigeria (2013) in her National policy on education stated that the Federal Government of Nigeria has adopted education as an instrument per excellence for effective national development. By that policy declaration, it is evident that Nigeria believes in the efficacy of education as the vehicle for individual and national development.

Unfortunately, the belief has been turned down due to scarcity of resources which include financial resources. In the 70s and 80s, after the takeover of schools by the government, Nigerian citizens believed that the government owned schools which include secondary schools are basically the concern of the government, therefore should take care of them.

Along the line, things started falling apart and the centre seem not to be together again. The entire education system appeared to be in a deplorable situation with dilapidated buildings, children staying under the mango trees to study, inadequate and unqualified teachers and a host of other horrible conditions. The deplorable conditions may have brought about the introduction of PTA/SBMC, Old Students/ Alumni, Community and other intervention programmers. The intervention of the aforementioned stakeholder's outside Government in the extent to which they provide fund for the sustenance of the system is yet to be determined. Hence, the need for the present study on "Stakeholders participation on the funding practices of public secondary schools in Enugu state".

Purpose of the Study:

The study was set to investigate "stakeholders' participation in the funding practices of public secondary schools in Enugu state". In particular, the study sought to:

- (1) Ascertain the extent of old students' participation in the funding practices of public secondary schools' in Enugu state.
- (2) Determine the extent of PTA/SBMC participation in funding practices of public secondary schools' in Enugu state.
- (3) Examine the extent of community participation in the funding practices of public secondary schools' in Enugu state.

Research Questions:

The following research questions guided the study:

- (1) What is the extent of the old students' participation in the funding practices of public secondary schools' in Enugu State?
- (2) What is the extent of PTA/SBMC participation in the funding practices of public secondary schools' in Enugu State?
- (3) What is the extent of community participation in funding practices of public secondary schools' in Enugu state?

Hypotheses:

The following hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance.

HO₁ There is no significant difference in the mean scores of male and female principals on the extent of old students' participation in the funding practices of public secondary schools in Enugu State.

HO₂ There is no significant difference in the mean scores of male and female principals on extent of PTA/SBMC participation in the funding practices of public secondary schools in Enugu State.

HO₃ There is no significant difference in the mean scores of male and female principals on the extent of community participation in the funding practices of public secondary schools in Enugu state.

Method

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study which was on "Stakeholder's Participation in the Funding Practices of Public Secondary Schools in Enugu State". Three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. The population for the study was 297 principals representing 297 public

Research Question 1: What is the extent of old students' participation in the Funding Practices of Public Secondary Schools in Enugu State?

Table 1: Mean responses of respondents on the extent of old students' participation in the funding Practices of Public Secondary School Education.

secondary schools in Enugu State. The entire population was used due to its adequate size. Data was collected using 19 item structured questionnaire developed by the researchers titled "Stakeholders Participation in the Funding Practices Questionnaire (SPFPQ)". The instrument was of two sections; A and B. A is for bio data of the respondents while B addressed the research questions. The instrument was face validated by three experts; two from the Department of Educational Management and one from Mathematics and Computer Science Education Department (measurement and evaluation option), all from Faculty of Education, Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT), Agbani. Reliability coefficient of .74 was established using cronbach Alpha reliability estimate. 297 copies of questionnaire were distributed using two research assistants who were briefed on the modalities for the distribution and retrieval. Out of the whole lot distributed, only 290 copies of the questionnaire were returned, giving a return rate of approximately 98%. Mean with standard deviation was used to answer the research questions while t test statistics was used to test the null hypotheses at .05 level of significance. The study also made use of $n > 2.50$ as region of acceptance while $n < 2.50$ as region of rejection for the research questions.

Results

The analysis was made using mean with standard deviation while t-test was used to test the null hypotheses at the appropriate degree of freedom.

S/N	Old Students:	Male Mean	Male SD	Female Mean	Female SD	Average Mean	Average SD	Decision
1	Provide facilities (seats, tables)	3.00	.93	2.58	1.24	2.79	1.09	A
2	Provide sporting facilities	3.27	.88	2.83	.94	3.05	.91	A
3	Supply instructional materials (science kit, etc.)	2.06	.83	1.67	1.07	1.86	.89	D
4	Sponsor student's scholarships	2.27	.88	2.42	1.08	2.35	.98	D
5	Construct classroom blocks	2.80	.87	2.83	.72	2.82	.80	A
6	Construct ICT blocks/centres	2.53	1.24	2.75	.97	2.64	1.11	A
7	Dug boreholes	2.40	.91	2.17	.72	2.29	.82	D
		2.62	.93	2.50	.96	2.56	.95	A

Table 1 above shows the mean scores of respondents (principals) on the extent of old students' participation in the funding Practices of Public Secondary School Education. Notably, both male and female principals agreed that old students provide facilities (seats and tables); provide sporting facilities; construct classroom blocks and as well; construct ICT blocks/centres for the secondary schools. This is because their mean scores of 2.79, 3.05, 2.82 and 2.64 exceeded the judgment base of 2.50. Meanwhile, the respondents disagreed on the items stating that old

students supply instructional materials (science kit, etc.); sponsor students; and dug boreholes for their secondary schools. This is because their mean scores of 1.87, 2.35 and 2.29, were below the judgment base of 2.50. Notwithstanding these, the principals generally agreed that the old students do really participate in the funding Practices of Public Secondary School Education in Enugu State. This is because, the general mean score of the cluster is 2.56 which exceeds the judgment base of 2.50.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female secondary school principals on the extent of old students' participation in the funding practices of public secondary schools in Enugu State.

Table 2: t-test Analysis of Male and Female principals on the extent of old students' participation in the funding practices of public secondary schools in Enugu State.

Status	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	t-cal	Decision
Male	155	2.62	.93	295	1.98	1.55	Do not
Female	142	2.50	.96				Reject H ₀

From the Table, it could be seen that the t-cal of 1.55 is less than the t-value of 1.98, the researcher therefore did not reject the null hypothesis and states that, there is no significant difference between the mean scores

of male and female principals on the extent of old students' participation in the funding practices of public secondary schools in Enugu State.

Research Question 2: What is the extent of PTA/SBMC participation in the Funding Practices of Public Secondary Schools in Enugu State?

Table 3: Mean responses of respondents on the extent of PTA/SBMC participation in the funding Practices of Public Secondary School Education.

S/N	PTA/SBMC:	Male Mean	Male SD	Female Mean	Female SD	Average Mean	Average SD	Decision
8	Provide school blocks	2.07	.80	2.00	.74	2.04	.77	D
9	Provide school bus	2.00	.93	2.25	.87	2.13	.90	D
10	Pay salaries of teachers they employ	2.13	1.06	1.83	.84	1.98	.95	D
11	Supplement government allocation through P.T.A levy	2.50	.83	3.25	.87	2.88	.85	A
12	Organize fund raising activities	2.13	.64	2.42	.79	2.23	.72	D
	Cluster Result	2.17	.85	2.55	.82	2.36	.84	D

Table 3 above shows the mean scores of respondents (principals) on the extent of Parents teachers association/ School based management committee (PTA/SBMC) participation in the funding Practices of Public Secondary School Education. Worthy to note is that, both the male and female principals agreed on the supplement of government allocation through P.T.A levy as the extent of PTA/SBMC participation in the funding Practices of Public Secondary School Education. This is because its mean score of 2.88 exceeds the judgment base of 2.50. Meanwhile, the general cluster agreed that PTA/SMBC provide school blocks, provide school buses, pay salaries of teachers they deployed, and organize fundraising

activities. This is because their mean scores of 2.04, 2.13, 1.98 and 2.23 did not reach the judgment base of 2.50. Generally, both male and female principals disagreed with the fact that parents’ teachers’ association/ school based management committee (PTA/SBMC) participate in the funding practices of Public Secondary School Education since the mean score is 2.36 and is below the judgment base of 2.50. Notwithstanding, the female principals agreed to Parents’ Teachers’ Association/School Based Management Committee (PTA/SBMC) participation in the funding Practices of Public Secondary School Education since their general mean score of 2.55 exceeds the judgment base of 2.50.

H02: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female secondary school principals on the extent of PTA/SBMC participation in the funding practices of public secondary schools in Enugu State.

Table 4: t-test Analysis of Male and Female principals on the extent of PTA/SBMC participation in the funding practices of public secondary schools in Enugu State.

Status	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	t-cal	Decision
Male	155	2.17	.85	295	1.98	5.55	Reject H0
Female	142	2.55	.82				

From the Table, it could be seen that the t-cal of 5.55 is greater than the t-value of 1.98, the researcher therefore rejects the null hypothesis and states that,

there is a significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female principals on the extent of

PTA/SBMC participation in the funding practices of public secondary schools in Enugu State.

Research Question 3: What is the extent of community participation in the Funding Practices of Public Secondary Schools in Enugu State?

Table 5: Mean responses of respondents on the extent of community participation in the funding practices of Public Secondary School Education.

S/N	Community:	Male Mean	Male SD	Female Mean	Female SD	Average Mean	Average SD	Decision
13	Provide school blocks	2.27	.80	2.75	.97	2.51	.89	A
14	Pay community teachers	2.07	.8-0	1.58	.90	1.83	.85	D
15	Provide seats/tables	2.33	.98	1.83	.84	2.08	.87	D
16	Pay security guards	2.07	.88	2.08	1.31	2.08	1.69	D
17	Organize fundraising activities	2.07	1.10	1.67	.99	1.87	1.05	D
18	Provide sporting facilities	2.27	.88	2.58	1.24	2.43	1.06	D
19	Sponsor indigent students	2.20	.86	2.00	.95	2.10	.96	D
		2.18	.90	2.07	1.03	2.13	.97	D

Table 5 above shows the mean scores of respondents on the extent of community participation in the funding practices of Public Secondary School Education in Enugu State. It is worthy to note that, both the male and female principals disagreed with the fact that the community pay community teachers, provide seats/tables, pay security guards, organize fund raising activities and sponsor indigent students. This is because, their mean scores of 1.83, 2.08, 1.87, 2.43 and 2.10 are all below the decision base of 2.50. Meanwhile, the female principals agreed that the community provide school blocks, and also provide

sporting facilities. This is based on the mean scores of 2.75 and 2.58 which both exceeded the judgement base of 2.50. Generally, the male and female mean scores for provide school blocks exceeded 2.50 since it is 2.51. This makes it the only item agreed upon, as where the community participates in the funding practices of public secondary school education in Enugu State. Notwithstanding these, the cluster mean score of 2.13 shows that both male and female principals disagreed with the fact that the community participates in the funding practices of public secondary school education in Enugu State.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference between the mean score of male and female secondary school principals on the extent of community participation in the funding practices of public secondary schools in Enugu State.

Table 6: t-test Analysis of Male and Female principals on the extent of community participation in the funding practices of public secondary schools in Enugu State.

Status	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	t-cal	Decision
Male	155	2.18	.90	295	1.98	1.39	Do not
Female	142	2.07	1.03				Reject H ₀

From the Table, it could be seen that the t-cal of 1.39 is less than the t-value of 1.98, the researcher therefore did not reject the null hypothesis and states that, there is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female principals on the extent of community participation in the funding practices of public secondary schools in Enugu State.

Discussion of Findings

On the extent of old students' participation in the funding practices of public secondary schools in Enugu State, it was revealed that they participate to a great extent in providing facilities such as seats, tables, sporting facilities, supply instructional materials (science kits, etc.), construct classroom blocks and as well construct ICT blocks/centres. Although, they disagreed with the participation in sponsoring students and digging boreholes, it does not necessarily mean that they do not assist but their participation was to a low extent. In essence, the old students really help their alma mater. This is in line with Obi (2019) who asserted that Alumni participation in secondary education management in Anambra State, Nigeria include, decision making, fund raising, acquisition of lands, staff and students welfare, erecting buildings, provision of material resources and fencing of school compound. It is also in line with Nwangwu (2015), who reiterated that old students' associations and other voluntary agencies participate in the management and sustaining education in the states. Intervention by Alumni groups therefore is a welcome idea that will help to enhance quality education in Nigeria. Nwakpa (2016) stated that effective use of the Old Students' Association by the school authority is always very helpful and healthy to the school since the association normally provides both cash and materials for the growth and development of their alma-mater. In that case, every good school principal utilizes this source to finance his school.

On the extent of PTA/SMBC participation in the funding practices of public secondary schools in Enugu State, the respondents agreed that the

PTA/SBMC only supplement government allocation through PTA levy. The respondents did not concur with the statement that PTA/SBMC provide school blocks, provide school bus, pay salaries of teachers they deployed and organize fundraising activities. Notwithstanding, Onderi and Makori (2017) maintained that parental school participation consists of activities like communicating with educators and other school personnel, volunteering at school, attending school events and assisting in academic activities at home. With proper involvement of parents in decision making, the constructive features bound agree to provision of educational materials, proper payment of school fees, facilitation of good teachers, high level of discipline, proper supervision of students' academic work, successful completion of school infrastructural project, order in school activities and less absenteeism. The implementation of policies at secondary school level is done with the involvement of all concerned stakeholders, the parents being a party. A case in point is the policy making and the implementation of school infrastructural projects at the secondary level of education that the major financiers for secondary school projects are the parents. This was through payment of school fees and PTA levies. Also, Yusuf (2012) in Analaba and Jack (2023) reported that the Parents Teachers Association (PTA) complements the government's efforts in the provision and maintenance of infrastructure in the schools. Despite the laudable roles of PTA in secondary schools, it appears that the problems of maintenance of the schools still thrive and it therefore presupposes that the roles of the PTA/SBMC can be strengthened in order to enhance better community participation in the schools since they are stakeholders that have interest in education and also have serious concern about a society or nations' educational activities.

On the extent of community participation in the funding practices of public secondary schools in Enugu State, the respondents agreed with the fact that the community only assists in the provision of school

blocks. They maintained that the community does not pay community teachers, provide seats/tables; pay security guards, organize fundraising activities, provide sporting facilities, and sponsor indigent students. Nwakpa (2016) stated that Community involvement is crucial. The school administrator cannot successfully run the school in isolation without the involvement of the community people. The community will help the school in carrying out its policies especially in the area of discipline and settlement of disputes involving both the students, staff and community. The community could be used to supply both free and cheap labour to the school if cordial relationship exists between the school and the community. Emenala and Ibekwe (2015) opined that school community include: parent teachers' association, business organisation, board of governor, religious organization, town unions, alumni association among others. Notably, the authors continued that the Community involvement in the funding of secondary education came as a result of absence or lack of facilities, teachers and general poor State of secondary schools in certain communities. Nakpodia (2016) on the issue of community funding stated that, community involvement in the funding of secondary education includes bodies like Parent Teachers Association, old boys' and girls' association, community progressive unions, youth wings, among others. There is therefore, need for community participation in funding secondary schools to enhance achievement of educational goals.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, though the stakeholders do not live up to expectation in almost all the funding practices listed, that does not mean that they do not support public secondary schools in Enugu

State. What is required is encouragement and public awareness on the need for active participation in the funding practices as this will enhance the functionality of the educational system in Enugu State Public Secondary Schools and beyond.

Recommendations:

Based on the findings the following recommendations were made:

- (1) Stakeholders in education should be encouraged for active participation in the funding practices of public secondary schools in Enugu State to enhance the output.
- (2) The principals' of public secondary schools in Enugu State should create public awareness on the need for PTA/SBMC active participation in the funding practices of their schools.
- (3) School Community relationships should be strengthened by the principals for active community involvement in funding practices as required by the school.

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